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The Factors Affecting Migration Behavior of Workers at Vietnam Garment Enterprise

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Abstract

This study is conducted to identify and evaluate the factors affecting the migration behavior of workers in garment enterprises in Vietnam. The subjects selected for the survey are workers who are working at many garment enterprises in some cities and provinces such as Hanoi, Ho Chi Minh, Bac Ninh, Nam Dinh, and Binh Phuoc... By conducting a survey to collect opinions from 312 employees and using SPSS statistical software to test the hypotheses; based on SEM linear structural model with 3 groups of factors affecting the intention to migrate to find job workers and consider the impact of the intention to migrate on the decision to migrate off the workers, the research results show that the factors "Behavior"; "Subjective norm" and "Perceived behavioral control" have a positive impact on the intention to migrate of garment workers with the impact level of +0,523; +0.73; +0.439; and the factor "Migration intention of garment workers" has a positive correlation to "Migration behavior of garment workers" with an impact level of +1.0, meaning the variation of intention to migration will lead to a corresponding change of migration behavior. From the testing, analysis, and evaluation of the factors affecting the migration intention and behavior of workers in Vietnamese garment enterprises, the research team has made some exchanges and discussions to attract more employees to the garment industry, contributing to promoting economic growth and creating sustainable jobs for workers.

Keywords: Impact Factors, Migration, Job-Seeking, Workers, Garment Enterprises, Vietnam

1. Introduction

Migration is an element of development, especially in developing countries. Studies have shown that the main reason for migration is economic and the main type of migration is job-seeking. Migration is a driving force as well as a result of a country's social-economic development.

The International Organization for Migration (IOM, 2018) defines "A migrant as a person who is moving or has moved across international borders or within a country far from his or her usual place of residence, regardless of (1) whether the person has legal status; (2) whether migration is voluntary or involuntary; (3) what are the causes of migration; or (4) how long do they resident".

According to the World Bank (2016) “Internal migrants are people who have moved across administrative boundaries within a country’s borders.” The United Nations provides a guideline for measuring internal migration which defines “internal migration as the movement from one defined area to another that occurs within a specified period and relates to change of residence” (UN, 1970).

Textiles and garments are considered key sectors of many economies. The trade scale of the global textile and garment market accounts for 8 - 8.8% of the total global trade, by value, reaching about 1,400 - 1.550 billion USD. Vietnam's textile and garment industry is also one of the key export industries and plays an important role in the growth of the economy, accounting for 12 - 16% of the country's total export turnover.

The textile and garment industry currently employs about 3 million industrial workers, accounting for over 10% of the country's industrial workers, is an industry with a large number of workers, attracting workers from the countryside to big industries. However, the human resource level of textile and garment enterprises is still low (with 84.4% of workers having a general education), while workers with a university degree account for only 0.1%... (Ministry of Industry and Trade, 2021); Human resources of garment enterprises in big cities and industrial areas are quite a lot of migrants from other localities. The situation of quitting jobs happens a lot, making it difficult for businesses to take care of their lives and retain employees. Therefore, learning about the factors affecting migration behavior approaching from behavioral theory will determine the level of impact of these factors. Therefore, the research team recommends some solutions to attract and ensure human resources for garment enterprises which have both theoretical and practical significance.

2. Theoretical Basis and Research Overview

The research team considers two models related to behavioral theory:

Firstly, the *Theory of Reasoned Action - TRA (Theory of Reasoned Action)* is a research model according to the psychosocial point of view to identify the factors of conscious behavioral tendency. The model refers to two factors affecting behavioral intention, including (1) Attitude towards performing the behavior. An individual's attitude is measured by the individual's beliefs and judgments about the results of that behavior; (2) Subjective norms. The people around influence whether or not to perform the behavior. The impulse to do so is due to the influence of those around (Fishbein, M & Ajzen, I. 1975).

Secondly, the *Theory of Planned Behavior model - TPB (Theory of Planned Behavior)* is built from the original theory of TRA, adding cognitive factors to control behavior along with two factors of attitude and subjective norm to behavioral intentions. Perceived behavioral control is an individual's perception of how easy or difficult it is to perform a behavior (related to the availability of necessary resources, knowledge, and opportunities to perform the behavior). Ajzen, I. 1991).

The team also overviews some research related to migration behavior. Which, research by Nguyen Quoc Nghi, Ngo Thanh Thuy, and Huynh Truong Huy (2010) shows the actual situation of labor migration in Hau Giang province and the factors affecting labor migration decisions in Hau Giang province. The logistic model is used and includes the variables of people of working age (with a positive relationship), production area (with a positive relationship), annual income (with a negative relationship), and variable income. The dummy shows the influence of natural conditions (with a negative relationship), and the dummy variable indicates the local underemployment situation (which has a positive relationship).

Research by Nguyen Thi Phuong Thao, Nguyen Ngoc Nam, and Nguyen Thi Thuy Dat (2020) shows that the main reason for the migration phenomenon is economic and the main type of migration is labor migration. The research team uses Logit regression to estimate the probability of household migration through the use of panel data from the living standard survey dataset. The research model proposed with variables belongs to the demographic characteristics of the household head and the characteristics and economic status of the household. The results show that the factors belonging to the demographic characteristics of the household head and of the household strongly affect the migration trend of the household.

Ravenstein, E. G., (1885) founded the study of theories of migration using census data in England and Wales. He argues that migration is closely connected with "push-pull" factors. Push factors such as low wages, high unemployment rate, and lack of health care factors, and pull factors such as high wages, and many jobs cause people to leave their residence. In other words, the main reason for migration is better external economic opportunities. Ravenstein also found that migrants tend to move to urban areas, rural people migrate more than urban people, women migrate more than men, and men often migrate farther. and most migrants are adults. Moreover, migration increases with economic, commerce, and industry development. The improvement of transport conditions increases the number of migrants.

Later studies inherited the content of Ravenstein to identify the factors that promote migration. Accordingly, the push factor is related to the place of departure (place of origin) of migrants. This factor includes low wages, high unemployment rate, lack of health care factors at the place of departure, political factors (political, ethnic, and national conflicts), economic, and cultural factors. Lee, E. S., 1966), low labor productivity and labor surplus in the agricultural sector (Lewis, W. A., 1954.; Lee, E. S., 1966). In addition, family debt pressure, poor education, and health systems, underdeveloped living conditions as well as the desire for family reunification are also among the factors " push" people to migrate (Le Bach Duong & Nguyen Thanh Liem, 2011); (Ngoc et al., 2017).

Empirical studies focus on explaining why people migrate, pointing out the characteristics of migrants. Studies agree that the main reason for migration is economic. However, in the study of the factors affecting the migration behavior of garment workers in Vietnam, the research team focuses on examining the factors affecting the migration behavior of workers according to the model. Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) Scales adjusted for garment industry specificity and referenced in migration studies were reviewed. To implement this implementation, in addition to the desk-based research method to review the rationale and collect secondary data, the research team conducted a sociological survey through survey to collect primary and secondary data. Using SPSS statistical software to test the data based on SEM linear structural model to consider 3 factors "Attitude", "Subjective norm", and "Perceived behavioral control" to the intermediate variable. in the model is "Migration intention of garment workers" and consider the impact on the dependent variable in the model as "Migration decision of garment workers".

3. The Model and Research Hypothesis

3.1. The research model

Based on the theoretical model of intended behavior - TPB of Ajzen, I (1991), along with the research review process, the authors build a research model on factors affecting the migration behavior of workers in the garment industry as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Proposed research model

Source: Proposal of the research team

3.2. Hypothesis and research scale

Hypothesis H1: Attitude toward migration has a positive relationship with the intention to migrate garment workers.

Hypothesis H2: Subjective norm has a positive correlation to the migration intention of garment workers

Hypothesis H3: Perceived behavioral control has a positive impact on the migration intention of garment workers.

Hypothesis H4: The migration intention of garment workers has a positive impact on the migration decision of garment workers.

The research scale is shown in Table 1 below.

Table 1: The basis for forming variables and factor scales in the model

Order	Code	Observed variable	Reference source
I	TD	Attitude	<i>Fishbein & Ajzen (1975); Ajzen (1991); Taylor & Todd (1995)</i>
1	TD1	I like migrating to find a job	
2	TD2	I am excited to find a job	
3	TD3	I am interested in finding a job	
4	TD4	Migration to find a job gives me excitement	
5	TD5	Migration to find a job gives me a lot of benefits	
II	CCQ	Subjective norm	<i>Fishbein & Ajzen (1975); Ajzen (1991); Taylor & Todd (1995)</i>
6	CCQ1	My migration to find a job is influenced by family members	
7	CCQ2	Most of my friends think that I should migrate to find a job	
8	CCQ3	There is a lot of information about the work of the garment industry in the place where I plan to move	
9	CCQ4	Many people around me migrate to find a job	
10	CCQ5	The place where I migrated to find a job has many acquaintances working there	
III	KSHV	Perceived behavioral control	<i>Ajzen (1991); Taylor & Todd (1995);</i>
11	KSHV1	I can look for a job	
12	KSHV2	I learn about the places I plan to migrate	
13	KSHV3	I am willing to ask a brokerage center / to ask relatives to help me find a job in the place where I intend to migrate	
14	KSHV4	I spend time and necessary resources to get job information about where I plan to move	
IV	YD	Migration intentions of garment workers	

15	YD1	Migration to find a job is the idea I have thought before	<i>Fishbein & Ajzen (1975); Ajzen (1991); Viswanath V, Michael G. Moris, Gordon B. Davis & Fred D (2003)</i>
16	YD2	I have prepared to find a job	
17	YD3	I expected to find to suitable job	
18	YD4	I am ready to migrate when I have chance	
V	QD	Migration behaviors of garment workers	<i>Taylor & Todd (1995); Viswanath V. Michael G. Moris, Gordon B. Davis & Fred D (2003)</i>
19	QD1	Migration to find a job is a reasonable decision	
20	QD2	Migration to find a job is an excellent decision	
21	QD3	Migration to find a job is a correct decision	
22	QD4	Migration to find a job is a necessary decision	
23	QD5	Satisfied about migrating to find work	

Source: Summary and recommendations of the research team

4. Collecting Methods and Analyzing Research Data

4.1. Measure variables and select research samples

The research is carried out based on a combination of qualitative and quantitative research. From the theoretical review and empirical studies, the research team identified 3 factors affecting the migration intention to find a job as a garment worker including Attitude (TD); Subjective norm (CCQ); Perceived behavioral control (KSHV), and the migration intention to find job variables of garment workers (YD) are the intermediate variables affecting the variable of employment migration behavior of garment workers (QD).

Next, the research team conducted a preliminary survey, the author discussed 2 groups of workers, each group including 3 workers who are garment workers working in industrial zones in Hanoi and Ho Chi Minh City. Discussion using a preliminary scale with factors affecting the migration intention and decision referencing from previous studies. The participants in the discussion were free to give their opinions on the aspects of the intention and decision to migrate for work. The preliminary study sample size is 6 (n=6). Preliminary research results are used to complete the research questionnaire and research model.

A quantitative research method was conducted to collect the opinions of garment workers on the intention and decision to migrate. The questionnaire is built based on preliminary research results and uses Likert5-level questions. Due to the limitation of survey time, the author used a convenient sampling method. The sample size was determined according to the rule of Comrey and Lee (1992), and also refers to the rule of Hoang Trong & Chu Nguyen Mong Ngoc (2005). With 23 parameters (observed variables) to conduct factor analysis, the minimum number of samples needed is $23 \times 5 = 115$ observed samples. Because of collecting as many observed samples as possible to ensure the stability of the impact, based on the ability to collect samples, the research team decided to choose the number of observed samples as $n = 300$. To ensure sample size, the author issued 350 survey questionnaires, the number of votes collected was 320 votes, of which 312 valid votes were included in the analysis.

4.2. Research data analysis

Research data collected will be cleaned and analyzed with the support of SPSS 20.0 software with analytical techniques:

Descriptive statistics: Describe the characteristics of the research sample according to predefined distinguishing signs.

Test the reliability of the scale (Cronbach's Alpha): by Cronbach's Alpha coefficient and remove inappropriate variables. Variables with a total correlation coefficient of less than 0.3 or with Cronbach's Alpha value that is larger than the total Cronbach's Alpha value will be excluded. Scales with Cronbach's Alpha from above 0.6 are usable.

EFA exploratory factor analysis: allows reducing many interrelated variables into representative factors. Using the test method (Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin) and Bartlett to measure the compatibility of the surveyed sample. Factor analysis is significant when the KMO value is > 0.5 and the sig value < 0.05 ; Factor loading factors must be > 0.5 ; In case observed variable loads on both factors, the loading coefficients must be different > 0.3 , and this observable variable is included in the factor that it uploads the highest with the condition that the factor loading > 0.5 .

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA): The purpose is to assess the fit of the model with research data, thereby providing convincing evidence of convergent validity.) and discriminant validity of the theoretical structure through the Model Fit indexes. According to Hair et al. (2010), the indicators considered to evaluate Model Fit include:

CMIN/df 3 is good, and CMIN/df 5 is acceptable

CFI 0.9 is good, CFI 0.95 is excellent, CFI 0.8 is acceptable

RMSEA 0.08 is good, RMSEA 0.03 is excellent

Analysis of linear structural model SEM: The SEM model combines all techniques such as multivariate regression, factor analysis, and correlation analysis, allowing one to check the complex relationship in the model. The SEM model allows us to simultaneously estimate the elements in the overall model, and estimate the causal relationship between the latent concepts through indicators that combine both measurement and structure of the theoretical model stable (recursive) and unstable (non-recursive) relationships. measuring direct and indirect effects, including measurement error and residual correlation. With the confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) technique, the SEM model allows the flexibility to find the most suitable model in the proposed models. Similar to the CFA model, the SEM model also evaluates the linear structure through the Model Fit indexes.

5. The Research Result

5.1. Introduce the research sample

The subjects of the survey are workers in garment enterprises in some major provinces and cities of Vietnam and people from other localities who have migrated in search of work. The number of votes collected and put into analysis is 312. Some sample characteristics are described in Table 2 as follows:

Table 2: Describe the study sample

		Amount	Proportion(%)
Gender	Male	80	25.6
	Female	232	74.4
Age	15-18 years old	32	10.3
	>18-22 years old	116	37.2
	>22 years old	164	52.5

Source: Survey results of the research team

Classification by gender shows a large difference between males and females, with 80 males (25.6%) and 232 females (74.4%), which is consistent with the research results of Ravenstein, E. G., (1885) and the fact in Vietnam shows that garment workers still have a higher proportion of female workers. Most of the surveyed people are over

22 years old (52.5%), followed by 116 people from 18-22 years old (37.2%), and the number of people surveyed from 15-18 years old is only 32 people (10.3%).

5.2. Evaluate the quality and reliability of the scale

The results of testing the scale of factors using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient show that the coefficients are all more than 0.8 (Table 3), and the correlation coefficients of the total variables of the observed variables in the factor are all greater than 0.3. It shows that the study is relevant and reliable. Among the 5 groups of factors with the initial number of observed variables $X_m = 23$ variables, no scale is excluded, so the number of observed variables included in the model is $X_k = 23$ variables.

Table 3: The results of testing the reliability of the scale

Factor(Code)	Number of observed variables			Coefficient Cronbach's Alpha
	Before inspection	After inspection	Variables eliminated	
Attitude(TD)	5	5	0	0,895
Subjective norm (CCQ)	5	5	0	0,858
Perceived behavioral control (KSHV)	4	4	0	0,882
Intention (YD)	5	5	0	0,893
Decision (QD)	4	4	0	0,876
Total	23	23	0	

Source: Survey results of the research team

5.3. EFA exploratory factor analysis

The results of EFA analysis, at the Eigenvalue value greater than 1 with the extracted variance Principal Components and Promax rotation, the factor analysis extracted 5 factors from 23 observed variables with the extracted variance of 70.571% (more than 50%) meeting the requirements. The KMO coefficient has a value of 0.893 (>0.5), meaning the analysis is significant. The value sig = 0.000 (< 0.05) shows that the observed variables in the study are correlated with each other in the population and EFA factor analysis is appropriate.

Table 4: EFA factor analysis results

KMO and Bartlett's Test					
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy					.893
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square				4166.411
	df				253
	Sig.				.000
Pattern Matrix					
	Component				
	1	2	3	4	5

TD2	.891				
TD3	.878				
TD4	.869				
TD5	.816				
TD1	.723				
QD2		.914			
QD3		.888			
QD4		.785			
QD1		.772			
QD5		.690			
CCQ5			.882		
CCQ3			.812		
CCQ1			.799		
CCQ2			.759		
CCQ4			.723		
YD3				.901	
YD4				.889	
YD2				.872	
YD1				.814	
KSHV1					.903
KSHV4					.856
KSHV2					.847
KSHV3					.823

Source: Survey results of the research team

Thus, in the factor analysis process with Eigenvalues of 1,556 (>1), 23 initially observed variables are converged into 5 groups of factors: Attitude (TD); Subjective norm (CCQ); Perceived behavioral control (KSHV); Migration intention of garment workers (YD); The employment migration behavior of garment workers (QD) with the total variance extracted is 70.571% (> 50%) means that 70.571% of the variation of the data is explained by these factors.

5.4. Confirmatory factor analysis CFA

The CFA test aims to determine the convergent validity and discriminant validity of the theoretical structure through the Model Fit indexes.

According to the test results, $CMIN/df = 1.304 \leq 3$ is good, $CFI = 0.978 > 0.9$ is good and $RMSEA = 0.036 \leq 0.08$ is good. Thus, it can be seen that the observed variables have convergent values on the representative variables, and at the same time all variables have discriminant values, there is no autocorrelation phenomenon.

5.5. Tested by linear structural model SEM

Figure 2: Structural model SEM

Source: Test results of the research team

Based on the results of the confirmatory factor analysis of CFA and the proposed research model, the research team builds a linear structural model SEM and performs verification steps. The SEM model test results show that the index CMIN/df = 2,214 (≤ 3) is good, the index CFI = 0.936 (> 0.9) is good, the index RMSEA = 0.062 (< 0.08) is good. good. The indicators show that the analysis by SEM structural model is meaningful.

Identifying the SEM structural model is significant, and the research team continues to consider the significance level for the impact of the independent variable on the dependent variable (Table 5). All factors have a P value < 0.05 , showing that the impact of the independent variables on the dependent variable is statistically significant.

Table 5: Determine the significance level of the impact of the independent variable on the dependent variable

	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
Intention ← Attitude	.186	.038	4.847		
Intention ← Subjective norm	.235	.043	5.511		
Intention ← Perceived behavioral control	.195	.045	4.372		
Decision ← Intention	1.282.	.265	4.837		

Source: Test results of the research team

Examining the degree of impact of independent factors on the intention to migrate garment workers in Vietnam by standardized regression coefficient (Table 6) shows that the factor "Attitude towards migration" has a positive impact on the intention to migrate garment workers with an impact level of +0,523; The factor "subjective norm" has a positive correlation with the migration intention of garment workers with an impact level of +0.73; The factor "Perceived behavioral control" has a positive impact on the migration intention of garment workers with an impact level of +0.439; and the factor "Migration intention of garment workers" has a positive correlation to "Migration behavior of garment workers" with an impact level of +1.0, meaning the variable of migration intention will lead to a corresponding change in the decision to migrate. Hypotheses H1, H2, H3, and H4 are accepted.

Table 6: Identify the level of impact of factors

	Level of impact	Accepted hypotheses

Intention <---- Attitude	.523	H1
Intention <---- Subjective norm	.730	H2
Intention <---- Perceived behavioral control	.439	H3
Decision <---- Intention	1.000	H4

Source: Test results of the research team

5. Some Exchange Discussions

5.1. Discussing research results

The research results of the group have shown that the migration intention of garment workers is affected by 3 factors arranged in order from the factor with the most impact to the lowest, including (1) Subjective norm (+0.730); (2) Attitude (+0.523); (3) Perceived behavioral control (+0.439), and changes in migration intentions will lead to corresponding changes in migration behavior.

The factor "*Subjective norm*" has the strongest impact on the intention to migrate garment workers with an impact level of +0.730. This means that garment workers in Vietnam's intention to migrate are influenced by the people around them, if the impact level of the people around them increases by 1 unit, the worker's intention to migrate will also increase by 0.73 units.

Factor "*Attitude*" is the next factor that affects the intention to migrate garment workers with an impact level of +0.523. This means that the migration intentions of garment workers in Vietnam are influenced by the individual's beliefs and judgments about the outcome of their behavior. If trust and personal appreciation increase by 1 unit, the intention to migrate to find work will increase by 0.523 units.

The factor "*Perceived behavioral control*" is a factor that positively correlates with intending to migrate garment workers with an impact level of +0.439. This means that the migration intention of garment workers in Vietnam is influenced by the individual's perception of how easy or difficult it is to migrate to find a job. If workers realize that it is possible or easy to migrate as well as their ability to ensure living conditions and find a job, their intention to migrate increases and soon turns into a decision to migrate. The test results show that, when the perception of behavioral control increases by 1 unit, the employee's intention to migrate increases by 0.439 units.

In addition, the survey results also show that hypothesis H4 "*The migration intention of garment workers has a positive correlation to the migration behavior of garment workers*" is accepted. The garment workers who intend to migrate have migrated, so the impact point here is +1.0. It means that the variation of the intention to migrate will lead to a corresponding change in the decision to migrate.

5.2. Some suggestions from the research results

It is a fact that textile and garment workers are tending to move to new occupations with better working environments (especially service industries, and tourism ...). Therefore, human resources are always fluctuating, greatly affecting the production activities of enterprises, it is necessary to have solutions to attract workers, especially skilled workers for the industry.

The guarantee of income and a good working environment for the current employees of the garment industry are important factors for workers who are intending to migrate when they are under the influence of the factor "*subjective norm*" the largest according to the survey results. Because it is those who have a stable and satisfactory job in the garment industry that will be the best reference channel for information for those who are intending to migrate to find work.

“Attitudes” towards migration play the next role in influencing the migration behavior of garment workers. For workers to be willing to migrate to find jobs in the garment industry, it is required for those garment enterprises: Is necessary to put in place labor regimes and policies associated with a reasonable reward and punishment regime to encourage workers Self-disciplined, active in the production, and conscious of self-improvement of technical expertise. Regularly organize dialogues between employers and employees; creating an environment of consensus and close attachment between groups of workers in the implementation of production lines. Moreover, implementing the compensation regime by capacity based on consensus with employees. It is necessary to have policies to take care of workers' lives such as housing, entertainment, insurance, etc. so that workers can work long-term with enterprises, to be able to attract workers for the industry.

To reach the perception of migrant workers in the garment industry, and impact the factor “Perceived behavioral control” so that they have the intention to migrate and make a decision to migrate, the employer needs to develop an annual and multi-year labor recruitment plan. Labor recruitment information should be widely advertised in the mass media to attract workers from many regions and localities. The recruitment must fully and strictly comply with the provisions of the law. Having clear information about recruitment will be a reference channel for those who intend to migrate to find work.

The study is based on the theoretical model of intended behavior - TPB of Ajzen, I (1991), the results of model testing show the factors “Attitude towards migration”; “Subjective norm” and “Perceived behavioral control” have a positive impact on the intention to migrate of garment workers and the factor “Migration intention of garment workers” has a correlation impact on “Migration behavior of garment workers”. However, many other factors also have an impact on the migration of workers such as Government policy; Regulations of the local government on security and order, socio-economic development policies, and job availability in the homeland... in this study have not been mentioned but will be the objects and targets for the local government and the next research.

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